

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE “NOOSPHERIC MIND” AT THE SYSTEM OF MODERN INFOCOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

Mishuk S.

*Belarusian Scientific Research Institute of Documentation and Archival affairs,
Department of Archives and Records Management
Ministry of Justice, Republic of Belarus
Deputy Director for Research
Ph.D. in Philosophy, Associate Professor
Minsk, Republic of Belarus
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Abstract

The article analyzes the problems of the functioning of the system of information and communication technologies in the context of the theory of the noosphere of V. I. Vernadsky. The ICT system is considered as a naturally occurring and necessary element of the noosphere as a whole, and modern civilization as its stage. The emergence of the infocommunication technology system as a special planetary envelope leads to the release of humanity beyond the purely earthly evolution and turns the Earth itself into a subject of the Universe.

Keywords: noosphere, system, civilization, Universe, information and communication technology system, cosmism.

Academician V.I.Vernadsky's doctrine of noosphere as a new planetary shell resulting from conscious (and in this sense reasonable) human activity is one of those scientific theories, the meaning and significance of which are not lost or diminished over time. Although the very term ‘noosphere’ was introduced into scientific circulation by French scientists Edouard Leroy and Teilhard de Chardin, it was V.I.Vernadsky who created a consistent and holistic scientific theory, revealing the conditions and regularities of the emergence and development of this special stage of evolution of the planet Earth. Moreover, this theory revealed the qualitative certainty of not only those processes that were observed during the lifetime of its creator. On the contrary, with each new decade in the development of mankind as a whole, it demonstrates previously hidden substantive aspects and new heuristic possibilities. On the one hand, this theory allows presenting a number of its provisions as a methodological basis for the construction of macro- and megamodels of planetary processes, operating with which it is possible to reveal new regularities of development of structural elements of modern civilisation. On the other hand, this theory, even in its existing form, creates huge opportunities for rational analysis. It sets the main directions for the creation of a new conceptual and categorical apparatus necessary to reveal the essential regularities of functioning and development of the modern stage of human civilisation.

In our opinion, information and communication technologies at the present stage are one of the most important components of the noosphere as a planetary shell. In order to correctly analyse their role and significance in this capacity, it is necessary, in our opinion, to clearly fix at least two substantive interpretations of the concept of ‘noosphere’ in the works of V.I. Vernadsky.

Firstly, he interpreted the noosphere as a certain stage in the planetary development of the Earth. The

scientist emphasised on the natural, necessary for the Earth's further existence process of noosphere emergence as a universal planetary shell, based on the geochemical principle of ‘growth of geochemical energy’ put forward by him. He emphasised that the emergence of the noosphere as part of the biosphere is a natural phenomenon, much deeper and more powerful in its basis than the entire previous human history. V.I.Vernadsky understood the noosphere as a qualitatively special stage in the Earth's evolution, arising as a result of the realisation of the essential laws of the planet's development.

Secondly, the noosphere was also understood as a stage of reasonable transformation of the environment in which man lives. V.I.Vernadsky emphasised that the presence of consciousness as a necessary component of human subject-transformative activity does not automatically mean that this activity is carried out reasonably in the true sense of the word. Human activity can lead to undesirable, even dangerous for him/herself consequences. Therefore, with the emergence of the noosphere, i.e., when its capabilities are comparable with the actions of natural forces, it is absolutely necessary to develop the level of humanity's cognition of the laws of the surrounding world and realise the goals of its own evolution in unity with the evolution of the rest of the planet.

Besides, the fact of noosphere emergence as a fundamentally new planetary envelope also means a known separation of man from the processes of the Earth's evolution proper. (Here the connection of V.I. Vernadsky's theory with the ideas of Russian cosmism of the late XIX-early XX centuries is obvious). It is at this stage that mankind is able to overcome the Earth's gravity and leave the limits of the environment of its origin. In other words, human activity turns into a factor not only of terrestrial but also of cosmic evolution. Under such conditions, the importance of human rationality in the broadest sense of the word increases

manifold. And in this sense, the noosphere (exactly as a sphere of reason, as a reasonably organised sphere of humanity's habitat) should be understood not only as one of the planetary shells and a stage of earth evolution, but also as a goal of the future development of mankind. And this goal can be achieved on condition of understanding the human being not as a 'purely' planetary, earthly factor, but as a force that goes beyond the limits of a separate planet and becomes significant for the whole Universe in infinite time.

Thus, the noosphere was understood by V.I. Vernadsky not only as a stage of the Earth's development, as something completed. It was unambiguously interpreted as a certain ideal to which mankind should strive. Once emerged, the noosphere in this respect turns into a process that develops according to its own internal laws in constant active interaction with the surrounding reality. On the one hand, it is a continuation and expression of these regularities and, on the other hand, it is simultaneously their active reflection. This system builds its relations with the surrounding world not passively, but actively. And as it develops, it expands its own boundaries so much that it goes beyond its home planet, beyond the solar system and further into the Universe.

In his works, V.I. Vernadsky systematised the factors, the presence of which is required for the formation and successful functioning and development of the noosphere. Let us try to briefly analyse those of them, which correspond to the goals of our work and are directly related to the functioning of the information and communication technology system - 'sharp transformation of means of communication and information exchange' and 'freedom of scientific thought and scientific search from the pressure of religious, philosophical and political constructions' [3, p.38]. [3, c.38].

The emergence in the late twentieth century and functioning in modern conditions of the information society clearly demonstrates the importance of information and communication technologies as its system-forming element. The latter act as one of the most important factors of sustainable existence and further development of human civilisation. In this regard, it is impossible not to emphasise the depth of scientific foresight of V.I. Vernadsky, who not only put this factor in the second place in terms of importance, but also noted the impossibility to implement the first most important factor without it - 'human settlement of the entire planet'.

To study the real significance of this factor, we should consider its functioning in the context of the noosphere as a sufficiently formed planetary shell. At this stage, the action of its internal regularities can be clearly traced. Having emerged once, the noosphere begins to evolve as an independent system. Its inherent laws lead to the emergence and subsequent selection of such mechanisms, the need for which arises at a certain stage of development. Moreover, the most significant mechanisms appear most often in those structural elements of the noosphere that are essential for it, i.e. related, first of all, to the functioning of 'reason and knowledge'. The emergence of such innovative in nature elements stimulates the progress of human society

on a planetary scale not only indirectly. They are directly included in the evolutionary development of the entire Earth and become one of the most important internal components of this process. As a result of their impact, existing structures are also changing. These components turn out after some time to be independent 'branches' of evolution, the development of which is in many respects similar to reproduction and evolution of living organisms, when the emergence of some new factor, seemingly not too significant initially, may later give rise to fundamentally new directions. Vernadsky also drew attention to this regularity, noting that '...the course of scientific thought, for example, in the creation of machines... is absolutely similar to the course of reproduction of organisms'. [1, c.134]. These new elements naturally appear when there is a need for them. In other words, their very emergence in the corresponding historical time interval is already an objective regularity. These 'purely reasonable' innovations fulfil a very significant role - they are the immanent mechanism of the noosphere, which ensures its 'self-preservation' at a particular stage of development and the possibility of further progressive movement. It can be concluded that the noosphere, in order to ensure continuous sustainable functioning, possesses appropriate, inherent internal mechanisms of self-regulation and self-preservation. At the same time, it has the ability to form in the appropriate period of time within its own structure fundamentally new elements that allow to adequately solve the emerging internal contradictions and ensure further progressive development.

This general theoretical position is perfectly illustrated by the example of the emergence and development of the global telecommunication computer network Internet, which at the present stage of progress of human civilisation is the core of the entire system of information and communication technologies.

Based on rather narrow and private needs (in this case, the need of the US Department of Defense for a secure data transmission system), a certain local system is created. Gradually it develops and goes a little beyond the segment of the world civilisation initially assigned to it. However, its own laws of functioning give rise to a number of new elements, which in the end fundamentally change the meaning of this system and make it global in importance. At the same time, the creators of these elements do not initially even assume such a possibility.

This component of the noosphere, which has become global in scale and degree of influence on the entire human civilisation, appears precisely when the need for it is formed. In this case, almost instantly (in the scale of human history) information and communication technologies turn from a certain innovative (not very clear beyond a narrow circle of specialists) factor into a fairly commonplace component of civilisation perceived by society. Suffice it to note that the International Telecommunication Union developed an index of information and communication technology development by country in 2007 and has been presenting it annually since then. In other words, the quantitative parameters of these processes have already become a

standard element of statistics along with others. Therefore, it can be stated with all certainty that within ten to fifteen years info-communication technologies have turned from a specific element of the scientific and military production sphere into a component of everyday life of the majority of the world's population.

As a result, we can conclude that within the noosphere, as a realisation of its internal regularities, there emerges a component that objectively creates an opportunity to organise management on a planetary scale, to regulate processes within the entire Earth. At the same time, this element itself quickly shows that for its full-fledged functioning it also requires management mechanisms corresponding in scale and authority. Thus, the gradual maturation of global problems within the noosphere quickly enough generates (on the basis of realisation of its own internal laws inherent to it) the mechanism enabling their resolution. And once formed, this mechanism itself in its turn requires global instruments corresponding to it in scale and capabilities, clearly demonstrating their objective necessity. All this again stimulates further development of the processes of planetary evolution [2, p. 115].

We can say that at present the information society as a new stage in the development of mankind (and the noosphere) has entered the next stage - the system of information and communication (or info-communication) technologies as a necessary, 'cognitive and reasonable' structural component of modern civilisation has been formed. They represent a global-scale system of receiving (production), processing, storage, transmission, distribution, exchange and consumption (use) of information. And it is gradually beginning to show qualities that were not observed in the artificial systems created by mankind earlier.

These qualitative features of info-communication technologies cannot be considered in detail within the framework of the article. Therefore, we will try to briefly record some of them.

Firstly, the emergence of the system of information and communication technologies is a necessary and natural stage in the development of the noosphere. The new 'reasonable' shell of the Earth objectively required an all-encompassing system that would fulfil the function of a carrier of universal knowledge.

Without the information and communication technologies formed at the present stage, the noosphere cannot function holistically. As the noosphere itself genetically and logically completes the development of the biosphere, so the sphere of info-communication technologies is the result of the internal laws of the noosphere, a natural stage of its evolution, on the one hand, and a necessary stage of its further functioning and development, on the other. The emergence of such a component of the noosphere as information and communication technologies means the onset of a new stage of noosphere development. As a result, it is already possible to record the existence of a self-sufficient global mechanism in terms of structure and functions. This component logically completes the formation of the noosphere and makes it sufficiently complete. With the emergence of the sphere of info-communication technologies, the 'noos (mind)' component is finally

formed as a structural element of the noosphere, as a certain 'nervous system' of the entire human civilisation. It begins to really function not only as a set of 'personalised minds'. Info-communication technologies allow each individual, regardless of location, time, level of education, etc., to directly, actively, in real-time mode to be included in the universal planetary thought process not only potentially, but actually. (Obviously, when implementing this process, not all results are indisputably positive. There are also negative aspects.) A truly generalised mind emerges, simultaneously covering the entire surface of the Earth, simultaneously involving hundreds of millions and billions of people in its functioning. It becomes a truly 'planetary sphere' in its scale, in the levels of presence (from the lithosphere to the cosmos), in the depth of its influence on the processes occurring on the Earth, and in the speed of transmission of these influences.

Secondly, the system of info-communication technologies is an active element of the noosphere by its essence and mode of functioning.

Human society is fundamentally different from other known natural systems. Systems of inanimate and animate nature exist as long as the cumulative energy of external influences is less than the internal connections of the system itself; they function within the limits provided to them by the totality of elements of the external environment. In other words, their interaction with the external environment is passive in its essence. In fact, they act as another factor of nature, similar to the others.

Man, initially actively influences nature and changes it in accordance with his needs in the process of labour activity. And the latter can be successful only if the goals, means, methods and programmes of activity correspond to the laws of nature itself. Therefore, cognition of the surrounding world is a necessary element of human transformations, the role of which is historically constantly increasing. Successful human activity depends on the depth of cognition of the surrounding nature.

In the sphere of info-communication technologies the processes of obtaining and exchanging knowledge, which human society possesses, take place. It can be said that it is in this component of human civilisation that the processes characteristic of the human attitude to the world as a whole take place. Within this system, cognition takes place, goals are set, necessary programmes are developed, the results achieved are analysed for their compliance with the set tasks, and the necessary adjustment of all elements of human activity is ensured.

Thirdly, information and communication technologies are, in our opinion, the most dynamic component of the noosphere in comparison with other components. The processes of obtaining, processing, storage, transmission, distribution, exchange and use of information, both as obligatory elements of subject-practical, transformative activity of human society, and taken by themselves, in comparison with other components of civilisation, are the fastest and most mobile. As the functioning of human society itself (in comparison with

other components of nature) is the least limited by external factors, so human mind, its functioning is the fastest, the most dynamic, the least limited by external factors. It can be restrained only by the 'brakes' inside itself, i.e., natural limits of individual cognitive activity, concrete-historical limits of a certain stage of human cognition, ideals and norms of cognition developed within the limits of this or that epoch. But all these natural and cultural-historical limits actually refer to the mind itself, understood as both individual and social. Thus, the sphere of info-communication technologies, immanently capable of independently regulating, changing, and pushing back the technical and concrete-historical cognitive frameworks restraining it, is fundamentally more dynamic in its essence than those systems that depend primarily on external factors.

Fourthly, information and communication technologies by their essence are also a truly innovative component of the noosphere. The human mind is most fully realised precisely when mastering the new, previously unknown. In this sense, human cognitive abilities are most vividly realised in scientific cognition. Science as a form of truly human ability to reflect the world around us is not aimed at replicating the existing and mastered, but at the constant involvement in practice of previously unknown objects. This fundamentally innovative type of object determines the other essential characteristics of science as a certain system of knowledge. The system of info-communication technologies also has as a reference point of its development the constant mastering of new knowledge. At the same time, it creates unprecedented opportunities and conditions for such activity. The global spread of information and communication technologies makes it possible to make the newly acquired knowledge available, to ensure its comprehensive discussion, analysis and subsequent use. In this sense, the processes of replication and practical assimilation of already available knowledge are sharply simplified, which makes it possible to free up information resources previously used for these purposes. As a result, the cognitive capabilities of mankind are raised to a qualitatively new level, which, in turn, makes the noosphere even more 'reasonable'.

Fifth, the system of information technologies is an evolving element of the noosphere. The regularities that the noosphere possesses lead to the emergence of new mechanisms necessary for its functioning at a certain stage. Processes similar in many respects to evolutionary selection in living nature are observed. Many different means and procedures constantly emerge in this environment, and in the end, as it were, those that are required are selected and developed. In our opinion, the previously mentioned history of the emergence and development of the Internet is a rather illustrative exam-

ple of this type of processes. In this sense, info-communication technologies as the 'nervous system' of the noosphere act, first of all, as an active regulator of the ongoing transformations.

In addition, they fulfil the function of initiating change. Problems arising within the framework of information and communication technologies constantly require solutions corresponding to their degree of complexity. Thus, these technologies within the noosphere clearly lead to the emergence of new elements of the structure and procedures of its functioning. As a result, the noosphere seems to create certain 'defence mechanisms' that allow it to persist and evolve.

In this sense, the sometimes expressed rather paradoxical idea about the hypothetically possible purposeful use of human beings by software algorithms to realise this goal has certain heuristic possibilities. Its essence lies in the fact that algorithms 'perceive' the surrounding real world as a certain external environment. And since they cannot independently, directly and directly change their own properties, they do it indirectly, using a human as a tool. Algorithms periodically 'initiate' certain failures and errors in their work so that people, eliminating them, thereby improve the whole system of info-communication technologies. With all the external fantasy, this idea, nevertheless, can initiate quite interesting conclusions for understanding the real regularities of functioning and development of the virtual world.

Thus, infocommunication technologies in modern conditions increasingly demonstrate their intrinsic system-forming properties and actively extend them to other structural components of human society. At the current stage of human civilisation functioning, the system of these technologies ceases to be an auxiliary structure (albeit a very important one), providing mere information transfer within the noosphere. By the beginning of the XXI century, information and communication technologies have reached such a level of development that they themselves begin to set new parameters of the systemic organisation of other structural components of human civilisation (economic, social, political, spiritual). As a result, these elements are transformed in accordance with the norms, procedures and rules of construction, which are determined by the info-communication sphere.

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